

Linear polyethylene terephthalate oligomers toxicity in human primary cells and interactions with biomolecules

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Introduction

Food contact materials (FCMs) are all materials intended to come into direct or indirect contact with food. Beside intentionally added substances, FCMs also contain non-intentionally added substances (NIAS), such as reaction by-products, oligomers, break-down or degradation products, etc. There is yet no harmonized risk assessment of NIAS by food safety authorities/regulatory bodies worldwide. All plastic FCMs, including commonly used polyethylene terephthalate (PET), contain oligomers to some extent as their presence is unavoidable in their production.

Methods

- Methylated and non-methylated linear PET oligomers (monomer, dimer and trimer) were synthesized and characterized by ¹H and ¹³C NMR and high resolution mass spectrometry.
- PET oligomers solubility in common solvents, as well as in food simulants (D1 oil in water emulsions simulant and D2e fat simulant) was determined.
- PET oligomers interaction with proteins was examined by their dispersibility in food and serum protein solutions.
- PET oligomers interactions with DNA and cells was explored by monitoring of salmon sperm DNA melting curve, their cytotoxicity in peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) and uptake by monocyte-derived dendritic cells (MDDCs) were monitored

Results

Figure 1. Structures of synthesized methylated and non-methylated linear PET oligomers

Oligomer	L1+1	L1+1/Me	L2+1	L2+1/2Me	L2+2	L2+2/Me	L3+3	L3+2/2Me	mg/mL
Water	1.30	1.96	0.03	0.01	0.10	0.08	0.08	2.00e-003	<1000
Methanol	21.88	357.58	0.34	0.31	1.84	2.79	0.33	0.21	<100
Abs. Ethanol	23.56	307.61	0.53	0.21	2.16	3.58	0.42	0.26	<10
Acetonitrile	3.35	360.98	0.42	1.12	1.37	19.26	0.21	0.46	<1
DMSO	282.83	648.73	14.95	1.08	78.46	139.96	8.30	1.63	<0.1
Ethyl acetate	8.28	294.36	0.40	2.34	1.74	8.76	0.76	0.98	<0.1
Chloroform	0.67	969.11	0.18	83.11	0.12	118.18	0.48	11.02	<0.1
D1 (50% EtOH)	21.95	269.20	0.43	0.19	2.08	3.22	0.38	0.21	<0.1
D2e (95% EtOH)	12.69	54.82	0.20	0.08	1.25	0.57	0.21	0.05	<0.1

Figure 2. The solubility of synthesized PET oligomers in common solvents and food simulants at 25 °C.

Solubility in food simulants decreases with increase in methylation and the number of aromatic rings

All PET oligomers readily interact with food and serum proteins resulting in large protein-PET oligomer aggregates

Figure 4. In vitro cytotoxicity (24 h and 48 h) of non-methylated and methylated PET oligomers in PBMCs

Figure 5. Uptake of PET oligomers (5 µg/mL) by MDDCs after A. 4 h and B 20 h stimulation, expressed as SSC MFI. C. Uptake of PET oligomers (5 µg/mL) by MDDCs after 4 h stimulation in the presence of monensin.

PET oligomers are taken up by antigen presenting cells

Figure 6. DNA melting curves in the presence of non-methylated (left) and methylated PET oligomers (right). Incubation mixtures consisted of DNA (50 µg/mL) and 0.024 µmol/mL PET oligomers or DNA (50 µg/mL) and DMSO (control).

Methylated PET trimer bind to salmon sperm DNA, leading to significant destabilization of the DNA.

Summary and Conclusion

All PET oligomers tested in the study have a molecular weight below 1000 Da, thus being of interest for chemical risk assessment. Toxicity of linear PET oligomers depends on size and end-group chemistry. Despite low acute toxicity, PET oligomers form complexes with proteins and DNA and should be considered for risk assessment.

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